

The Responsibility of States for the Wrongful Setting Aside of Arbitral Awards

The 1958 New York Convention (the "Convention") has successfully granted international arbitration an advantage over other alternative dispute resolution ("ADR") mechanisms by providing an element of enforceability of arbitral awards. That has made arbitration the most favoured method of settlement of international commercial and cross-border disputes.

Yet in many instances, enforcement of an international arbitral award can be a challenging process when the national courts of the states where enforcement is sought wrongfully resist the recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards. In such cases, the New York Convention does not provide for any process to be followed by the party seeking enforcement of the award, which leaves the award creditor in a difficult position after a lengthy and costly legal battle.

Thereupon, award creditors suffering from such a dilemma must have an alternative relief to seek enforcement of the awards. Such alternative methods can be available in international law forums by invoking the state's responsibility for internationally wrongful acts.

This article will provide an overview of the enforcement process under the New York Convention and the extent of review of arbitral awards permissible to national courts under the Convention. Secondly, it will assess the implications of refusal of recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards to arrive at remedies available under public international law. Finally, it will discuss whether award creditors can invoke states' responsibility for the wrongful annulment of international arbitration awards under public international law considerations.

Recognition and Enforcement of Arbitral Awards Under the New York Convention

Article I (1) of the New York Convention stipulates that:

"This Convention shall apply to the recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards made in the territory of a State other than the State where the recognition and enforcement of such awards are sought, and arising out of differences between persons, whether physical or legal. It shall also apply to arbitral awards not considered as domestic awards in the State where their recognition and enforcement are sought"¹.

¹ Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (adopted 10 June 1958, entered into force 7 June 1959) 4739 UNTS 330 (New York Convention) Art I.

As prescribed by Article I (1) of the Convention it is clear that signatory states consent to recognizing and enforcing foreign arbitral awards resulting from arbitration proceedings conducted outside of their jurisdictions². In addition, Article III of the Convention obliges contracting states to “recognize arbitral awards as binding and enforce them in accordance with the rules of procedure of the territory where the award is relied upon...”³

However, the party seeking enforcement of an arbitral award under the New York Convention must fulfil certain requirements which are set out by Article IV to facilitate such enforcement. In that regard, the award creditor must at the time of applying for enforcement present to the relevant competent court the following:

- (a) The duly authenticated original award or a certified copy of it.
- (b) The original arbitration agreement as defined in Article II of the Convention or a certified copy of it.
- (c) A certified translation of the above-mentioned documents if they are made in a language different from the official language of the state where the application is presented⁴.

Nonetheless, the obligation of recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards bestowed upon states’ national courts by virtue of the New York Convention is not absolute. In some circumstances, national courts may have the power to refuse the recognition and enforcement of arbitral awards if it is proven that such awards satisfy one or more of the grounds of refusal specified by Article V of the Convention.

Conversely, Article V differentiates between certain grounds for refusal of recognition and enforcement. The first set prescribed by Article V (1) provides the grounds that can be relied upon by the party resisting enforcement or seeking annulment of the arbitral award. Secondly, Article V (2) provides for the grounds of refusal that are subject to the discretionary powers of the competent court.

² Albert Jan Van Den Berg, ‘The New York Convention of 1958: An Overview’ in Emmanuel Gaillard and Domenico Di Pietro (eds), *Enforcement of Arbitration Agreements and International Arbitral Awards* (Cameron May, 2008) 39.

³ The New York Convention 1958 (FN 1) Art III.

⁴ The New York Convention 1958 (FN 1) Art IV.

For the purpose of this essay, the focus will be directed to the grounds prescribed by Article V (2) by which national courts can exercise wider discretionary powers to determine the enforceability of the award. In this regard, Article V (2) states that:

“2. Recognition and enforcement of an arbitral award may also be refused if the competent authority in the country where recognition and enforcement is sought finds that:

(a) The subject matter of the difference is not capable of settlement by arbitration under the law of that country; or

(b) The recognition or enforcement of the award would be contrary to the public policy of that country⁵.”

In several instances, states may apply Article V (2) of the Convention wrongfully leaving the award creditor no relief but to seek enforcement of the award in another jurisdiction where the debtor has business or assets⁶.

However, if the award is issued against a local business or a state through a bilateral investment treaty (“BIT”) such an option may not be viable for the creditor. For example, in *Regent Company v. Ukraine*⁷, a limited liability company from Prague, Czech Republic, filed a lawsuit against Oriana, an open joint-stock company based in Kalush, Ivano-Frankivsk Region, with the majority of its shares owned by the State. COM claimed that Oriana had breached its contractual obligations regarding the processing of raw materials. The case was brought before the International Commercial Arbitration Court at the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Ukraine. On December 23, 1998, the Arbitration Tribunal issued a ruling (case AC no. 142y/98) ordering Oriana to pay COM \$2,466,906.47 in compensation⁸.

In July of 1999, COM applied to the Ivano-Frankivsk Regional Arbitration Court. Their objective was to prove that they were creditors of Oriana, based on the award given on December 23, 1998. However, on October 16, 1999, the Regional Arbitration Court denied COM's petition to start a bankruptcy process against Oriana.

⁵ The New York Convention 1958 (FN 1) Art V (2).

⁶ Deyan Draguiev, ‘State Responsibility for Non-Enforcement of Arbitral Awards’ (2014) 8(4) World Arbitration & Mediation Review. 577.

⁷ *Regent Company v. Ukraine*, App No. 773/2003 (Judgement, 3 April 2008).

⁸ *Regent Company v. Ukraine* (FN 4) 7, 8.

Regent Company (the “Applicant”) which had acquired the right to claim COM’s debt resulting from the award, then sought relief at the European Court of Human Rights under the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms dated 1950. Claiming that the state had breached the principles of fairness and civil rights under Article 6(1) and Article 1 of Protocol No. 1 of the Convention⁹.

In its determination of the matter, the court concluded that “it appears from the case file that no recent steps have been taken by the State authorities to remedy the situation in the present case. The Court is therefore of the view that the continued non-enforcement of the judgment debt at issue constituted a violation of Article 6 § 1 of the Convention¹⁰.”

The court unanimously ruled in favour of the applicant and decided that “(a) that the respondent State is to pay the applicant company, within three months from the date on which the judgment becomes final in accordance with Article 44 § 2 of the Convention, the outstanding amount of the arbitration award of 23 December 1998 still owed to it...;¹¹”.

It is evident that other remedies can be available for award creditors when the New York Convention enforcement process has been exhausted to no avail. However, the availability and attractiveness of the approach taken by Regent Company is not available for all aggrieved award creditors. According to Article 33 of the European Convention on Human Rights, “Any High Contracting Party may refer to the Court any alleged breach of the provisions of the Convention and the Protocols thereto by another High Contracting Party.”¹² Thereupon, a relief based on

⁹ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (adopted 4 November 1950, entered into force 3 September 1953) 2889 UNTS 213.

¹⁰ Regent Company v. Ukraine (FN 4) 60.

¹¹ Regent Company v. Ukraine, App No. 773/2003, Judgement, 3 April 2008. 5.

¹² Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (adopted 4 November 1950, entered into force 3 September 1953) 2889 UNTS 213. Art 33.

human rights claims will always depend on the position and nationality of the award creditor and is not widely available to all nationalities¹³.

In a similar case where the state of Bangladesh has wrongfully set aside an arbitral award in favour of the Italian Company Saipem S.P.A where Saipem had secured a favourable award against Petrobangla, the Bangladeshi national oil company; and the Bangladeshi national courts decided on the nullity of the award based on bias¹⁴. Saipem then initiated ICSID proceedings under the Bangladesh – Italy BIT (1990) based on indirect expropriation and denial of the right to arbitrate under the contract¹⁵.

Saipem argued that the actions of the courts of Bangladesh and Petrobangala are attributed to the states of Bangladesh and therefore the claims raised by the claimant should be admissible under the Bangladesh – Italy BIT (1990)¹⁶. The tribunal analyzed the attribution of the actions of the courts of Bangladesh and Petrobangala on the basis of the test adopted in *Impregilo v. Pakistan*¹⁷, and it held that the dispute falls within the jurisdiction of the ICSID under the the Bangladesh – Italy BIT (1990)¹⁸ and on the merits “The Respondent (Bangladesh) shall pay to the Claimant the sums of USD 5,883,770.80, and USD 265,000.00 and € 110,995.92 plus interest at a rate of 3.375% per annum from 7 June 1993”¹⁹.

Furthermore, resorting to other forums such as the ICSID and UNCITRAL on the basis of the BIT claim is not always as successful as the outcome in the Saipem case. An example of this is the Romak case where the award creditor suffered a similar situation to the Saipem case however the pursuit of remedy under the Switzerland – Uzbekistan BIT (1993) umbrella was not successful.

In *Romak v. Uzbekistan*, Romak S.A. a Swiss company and a group of companies that dealt with grain trading, entered into a contract with Romak S.A., for the supply of wheat. However, Romak

¹³ D Brian King and Rahim Moloo, ‘Enforcement after the Arbitration: Strategic Considerations and Forum Choice’ (Forum Shopping in the International Commercial Arbitration Context Conference, NYU’s Center for Transnational Litigation and Commercial Law, 28 Feb – 2 March 2013).

¹⁴ *Saipem v. People’s Republic of Bangladesh* (ICSID Case No. ARB/05/7).

¹⁵ *Saipem v. People’s Republic of Bangladesh* (ICSID Case No. ARB/05/7) ‘Decision on Jurisdiction and Recommendation on Provisional Measures’. III.

¹⁶ *Ibid.* 143.

¹⁷ *Impregilo v. Islamic Republic of Pakistan* (ICSID Case No. ARB/03/3).

¹⁸ *Saipem v. People’s Republic of Bangladesh* (ICSID Case No. ARB/05/7) ‘Decision on Jurisdiction and Recommendation on Provisional Measures’. 161.

¹⁹ *Saipem v. People’s Republic of Bangladesh* (ICSID Case No. ARB/05/7) Award 216.

faced several issues in receiving payment for the delivered goods. As a result, Romak commenced arbitration proceedings against their Uzbek counterpart in accordance with the contracts. The arbitration was conducted under the GAFTA and was concluded in favour of Romak S.A. Despite receiving an award from the arbitration, Romak was unable to enforce it in multiple countries, including Uzbekistan²⁰.

Romak initiated arbitration proceedings under the Switzerland – Uzbekistan BIT (1993) arguing that the actions of their counterparties in the deal can be attributed to the state of Uzbekistan as the buyers of wheat were State entities and were acting on behalf of the public to serve the public interest²¹. On the other hand, the State of Uzbekistan argued that the claims of the Claimant were contractual in nature and did not fall under the bilateral investment treaty between Switzerland and Uzbekistan²².

After its analysis, the Tribunal decided that it has jurisdiction *ratione personae* as the fact that Romak qualified as an investor was not in dispute. However, the Tribunal's jurisdiction *ratione materiae* was not present in the current case²³. therefore, the Tribunal dismissed Romak's claims for lack of jurisdiction²⁴.

Based on the above analysis, it can be said that invoking the responsibility of states for the wrongful setting aside of arbitral awards is not always available for the aggrieved award creditor. First, the award creditor cannot invoke such responsibility under human rights claims unless it qualifies as a High Contracting Party in the meaning of Article 33 of the European Convention on Human Rights. Secondly, to invoke a claim under a BIT the award creditor must qualify as an investor under the relevant BIT and the subject matter of the dispute must also qualify as an investment under the same BIT, which is not always the case²⁵.

Therefore, an alternative to the traditional methods must be explored and developed to resolve the dilemma if the above-mentioned solutions are not available to the award creditor.

²⁰ Romak S.A. (Switzerland) v. The Republic of Uzbekistan PCA Case No. AA280. Award. 13.

²¹ Romak S.A. (Switzerland) v. The Republic of Uzbekistan PCA Case No. AA280. Award. 118.

²² Romak S.A. (Switzerland) v. The Republic of Uzbekistan PCA Case No. AA280. Award. 132.

²³ Romak S.A. (Switzerland) v. The Republic of Uzbekistan PCA Case No. AA280. Award. 163

²⁴ Romak S.A. (Switzerland) v. The Republic of Uzbekistan PCA Case No. AA280. Award. VII.

²⁵ D Brian King and Rahim Moloo (FN 13) 20.

State to State Dispute Settlement as a Potential Remedy

According to Article 2 of the Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts, ‘There is an internationally wrongful act of a state when conduct consisting of an action or omission: (a) is attributed to the state under international law, and (b) constitutes a breach of an international obligation of the state²⁶.

If the aggrieved award creditor can establish that an arbitral award has been wrongfully annulled or wrongfully unenforced and was successful in attributing such wrongful action to the state where enforcement was sought a claim against the state can be brought before the International Court of Justice (ICJ). However, the challenging part is that claims before the ICJ can only be brought forth by another state pursuant to Article 34 (1) of the statute which reads as follows: “Only states may be parties in cases before the Court”²⁷.

In ‘Enforcement after the Arbitration: Strategic Considerations and Forum Choice’ D. Brian King and Rahim Moloo explored the option of diplomatic protection for the aggrieved award creditors when the enforcement of their awards has been halted by an internationally wrongful act of a state²⁸.

In their view, two types of claims can be brought against a state before the ICJ or State-to-State arbitration. First, a breach of the New York Convention in the meaning of Article 26 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties which states that “Every treaty in force is binding upon the parties to it and must be performed by them in good faith”²⁹. Secondly, a breach of the standard of treatment due to foreign nationals³⁰.

Nonetheless, resorting to diplomatic protection and State-to-State dispute settlement is a challenging process and is not always accessible³¹. For example, in 1907 a similar approach was taken to resolve disputes between states resulting from unlawful treatment by states to the nationals

²⁶ UNGA Res 56/83 (2001) Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts UN Doc A/RES/56/83. Art 2.

²⁷ Charter of the United Nations and Statute of the International Court of Justice (adopted 26 June 1945, entered into force 24 October 1945). Art 34 (1).

²⁸ D Brian King and Rahim Moloo (FN 13) 49.

²⁹ Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties. Art 26.

³⁰ D Brian King and Rahim Moloo (FN 13) 50.

³¹ D Brian King and Rahim Moloo (FN 13) 49.

of other states with the introduction of the Second International Peace Conference of 1907³². The convention introduced arbitration as a means of settling disputes between states to prevent military incursions in economic and commercial affairs³³. Article 37 of the Convention states that “International Arbitration has for its object the settlement of disputes between states by judges of their own choice and on the basis of respect of law”³⁴.

However, the feedback of individuals and investors at the time was not positive towards the inclusion of their home states in the resolution of investment and commercial disputes. The process of addressing claims related to investment disputes was often politicized, as some states chose not to pursue such claims to maintain positive diplomatic relations with the host states where the investments were made. Additionally, even if an investor's home state agreed to pursue the claim, significant delays could occur before the government initiated the arbitration process³⁵.

In conclusion invoking the states’ responsibility for international wrongful acts, specifically the wrongful setting aside of arbitral awards is an important aspect of international arbitration that needs to be developed and improved. Currently, there are several forums and approaches by which an aggrieved award creditor can find remedy and seek enforcement of awards that have been wrongfully annulled or set aside by states. First, the human rights approach is a viable option, but it is not accessible to everyone. Secondly, invoking a claim under ISDS and BITs is also a practical solution, but it does not fit all types of awards. Finally, resorting to the home state to bring a claim on behalf of the aggrieved party can be lengthy and burdensome on the part of the aggrieved award creditor. Thereupon, further development to the New York Convention or the development of a parallel system that would allow individuals to bring claims against states before international law forums can be a viable solution.

³² Convention for the Pacific Settlement of International Disputes (adopted 18 October 1907, entered into force 26 January 1910).

³³ David Collins, *An Introduction to International Investment Law* (Cambridge University Press 2017) 11.

³⁴ Convention for the Pacific Settlement of International Disputes (adopted 18 October 1907, entered into force 26 January 1910) Art 37.

³⁵ Nigel Blackaby and Constantine Partasides, *Redfern and Hunter on International Arbitration* (6th edn, OUP 2015) 443; Rudolf Dolzer and Christoph Schreuer, *Principles of International Investment Law* (2nd edn, OUP 2012) 233.

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